

THE CIRCULAR CONSUMER BEHAVIOR THROUGH INDUSTRY 4.0 TECHNOLOGIES IN A POST-PANDEMIC REALITY

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Abstract

Purpose – The objective of this study is to show how the Industry 4.0 technologies can unlock circular economy and how this can influence the consumer behavior, which changed by COVID-19 pandemic.

Methodology - The technologies under the umbrella of Industry 4.0 were identified, followed by choosing the ReSOLVE framework for circular economy. Then consumption behavior and end-of-life attitude were analyzed.

Findings – The 4th Industrial Revolution brought everything closer with better communication means and more interconnections which can provide patterns and correlations for more data-based decisions making in the future.

Research limitations/implications – There is still room for filling in the gap about the impact of Industry 4.0 on the circular consumer behavior, how it can enable it and where are the weak and strong points for further action.

Practical implications – The use of Industry 4.0 technologies and ReSOLVE framework can impact the circular behavior, increasing thus the circular economy adoption, being a viable option to explore for companies in order to achieve sustainability.

Originality/value – This article contributes to literature by assessing how Industry 4.0 technologies can unlock CE and how can influence the circular behavior.

Key words: circular economy; industry 4.0; consumer; ReSOLVE; end-of-life.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has strongly changed consumption behavior, determining a preference for products with efficiency features, from brands that contribute to society (people having health and environment awareness) so the sustainable development (SD) and circular economy (CE) are two essential parts for the future of humanity and for competitiveness of businesses (Das, 2022; Tao, 2022).

The paradigm of CE integration into industrial activities has as a baseline the reconfiguration of production and business models to become circular, for decreasing the negative impacts on the environment, health and society as a whole and meeting the behavioral shifts in consumers demands due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which and also increased the online collaboration and digital transformation.

This transition requires actions like redesign supply chains, efficient models in terms of energy, material use and emissions and is based on innovation and technology (Rada, 2017; Pacurariu, 2021). Technology as an enabler of CE should aim also to improve companies' sustainability, thus impacting the sustainability of society. With this goal, Industry 4.0 (I4.0) is a strong candidate as enabler to reach CE (Garcia-Muiña, 2018), integrating production systems in a horizontal and vertical way through the

use of live streamline of data, flexible and adaptive technologies for manufacturing processes and highly customizable (Rojko, 2020).

Methodology

To accomplish the paper purpose, an exploratory research has been conducted. Systemic literature review was chosen to show the links between technology adoption/use and the framework of CE. Furthermore, consumer identification is highly important for the relevance of the current study as it sets a context for further advancement into CE implementation. The analysis was articulated through a series of steps presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research framework for the current research

Results

Technologies in the Era of Industry 4.0

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is the outcome of new solutions which reduce the mechanical and the hardware aspects of industrial processes and emphasis the evolution of software application. It is the continuous development of IT-tools and systems with high storage capacities and transmission speeds (Lele, 2019). The main technologies and defining features can be seen in the Table 1 (Gölzer, 2017; Waslo, 2017; Kang, 2018; de Sousa Jabbour, 2018; Dalmarco, 2019; Ferreira, 2021; Hettiarachchi, 2022)

Table 1. I4.0 technologies

Additive Manufacturing (AM)	Technology which prints objects in a series of overlapping layers of material without having waste from cuttings.
Augmented Reality (AR)	Combination of 3D elements with spatial context, integrated in a virtual form. Offers the possibility for real-time processing of image projections to test new products or to improve processes.
Big Data&Analytics (BDA)	It consists in the advanced use and analyse of large volumes of data, aiming to uncover trends, patterns and correlations to help in the delivery of data-informed decisions.
Cloud manufacturing	Virtual platform in the form of a network used to share resources using cloud computing, internet and virtualization. It allows for accessibility to data, systems and equipment from any device or geographic location if it is connected to the internet.
Collaborative Robotics	Robots designed to work closely with humans and used for repetitive tasks, allowing human workers focus on problems that require problem-solving skills.
Cybersecurity	Systems which allow the protection of systems, equipment, networks and users from illicit intrusion. It foresees reliability and safety improvements of the traceability of products.
Internet of Things (IoT)	A network of physical things/objects (sensors, software and other technologies) with the purpose of connecting and exchanging data with other systems/devices over the internet.

Simulations	It is a virtual testing tool which improves the feasibility analysis of new products with testing options and training for employees.
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CE framework - ReSOLVE

CE has several value drivers – extending the products’ usage cycles, enhancing the utilization through sharing practices, resource productivity, closing the loops of materials through reuse, remanufacture, recycling, redesign, and preserving and regenerating the natural resources. To enable the drivers, the ReSOLVE framework was chosen for this research (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015; de Sousa Jabbour, 2018; Esmaeilian, 2020; Cagno, 2021).

Regenerate – it is enabled through biological cycles to facilitate energy and material circulation and to convert organic waste into sources of energy and secondary materials for different cycles.

Share – is the underlying base for sharing economy where goods are shared between individuals, not owned. The design of products should ensure they have a long lifespan and maintenance and repair is available to enhance re-use and extension until the end-of-life.

Optimize – requires a technology-centered strategy where digital technologies (sensors, automation, RFID, remote sensing etc.) are being used in the manufacturing to reduce waste generation, increase performance, efficiency and efficacy.

Loop – Technical cycles can restore the value of post-consumption products as it is the case with anaerobic digestion, as in the case of repair, reuse, remanufacture and recycling.

Virtualize – A strategy focused on services where the aim is to replace the physical products with dematerialized, virtual products.

Exchange – Substitution of old and inefficient products with renewable, advanced ones in order to optimize the continuous flow and availability of rare elements on the market.

Circular Behavior for Consumption

Consumers are key players in the field of CE, contributing to the adoption/rejection of CE implementation on the market and to the adoption of circular principles into their lifestyles and use them in the decisions they take (Rutitis et al., 2022). In this regard, they have the following roles through their consumption patterns (Esmaeilian, 2020):

Purchase behavior – for the circular products choice (used, remanufactured, green etc.).

Consumption behavior – customer’s behavior in terms of energy conservation, sharing, green consumption, waste prevention, reduced consumption and local choices.

End-of-life behavior – the action followed by customers at final stage of products life (repair, recycle, reuse, integration into trade-in programs, sustainable discard of objects).

Table 2. Industry 4.0 technologies in the CE framework ReSOLVE with their stage of implementation and consumption behavior

Technology	CE						Consumption		
	Regenerate	Share	Optimize	Loop	Virtualize	Exchange	Purchase behavior	Consumption behavior	End-of-life behavior
Additive manufacturing			x	x		x	x		
Augmented Reality			x		x				x
Big Data & Analytics		x	x	x			x	x	x
Cloud manufacturing		x	x		x			x	x
Collaborative Robotics	x		x			x			x
Cybersecurity		x	x				x		

Internet of Things	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Simulations	x		x		x				x

Discussion and Conclusions

Nowadays, in the era of digitalization and automatization, rapid progress is happening due to innovation in sensors, devices, networks and machine learning. This affects the whole society and environment, education, health and lifestyle, pinpointing the importance of SD which integrates technologies of I4.0, that have an even greater role in enabling CE design and implementation as it can be seen in Table 2.

Regeneration of materials can be fostered by I4.0 through the use of Collaborative robotics and IoT in the form of sensors and computer/telephone apps. Through prior Simulations, the optimal design of the operation management can be established and when at the desired stage, the plan is ready to be implemented (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2016).

The Sharing model - BDA can determine where the sharing economy presents the highest potential for development. Analyzing large volumes of data can also be useful for creating networks and connecting people with the same needs in terms of “want to be shared” products or services, enabling connectedness and facilitating communication. Additionally, IoT and Cloud manufacturing play a similar role. Websites and mobile apps have proved that people engage in finding others to connect and share information and the data retrieved can help better establish the product/service design for better utilization or replacement and increase customer satisfaction at the same time (Dev, 2020).

I4.0 technologies provide useful room for *Optimization*. Additive manufacturing (AM) reduces the material waste. 3D printing for instance leaves the smallest quantity of scraps possible. Collaborative robotics can also ensure efficiency in production where human errors are reduced. AR and Simulations can help design the most optimal plan from the incipient phases, detect industrial symbiosis opportunities and simulate the whole industrial process. As an addition, IoT, BDA, use of cloud networks and Cybersecurity optimize the collection process and objects (Hofmann, 2017). They are able to identify failures, can provide performance parameters for highest efficiency of machines, can be checked in real-life time to have an accurate picture of the process.

The *Loop* business model is a broad part of the CE especially significant for the extension of the circulation of materials and energy, with the closure of the loops at the end-of-life. AM can enable this through the use of recycled materials in the 3D printing processes. The loops can be narrowed down and closed through modular design for components with instructions of how they can be disassembled and recycled at the end of life. Moreover, sensors can provide product passports for each of the products with relevant information about their circularity. BDA can afterwards track down how circular products are, how they circulate in the physical space and where improvements can be made (Piccarozzi, 2018; Ferreira, 2021; Kamble, 2021).

As *Virtualize* is the transition from physical products to services, here Simulations and AR can establish the smoothest pathway to achieve this transition, having the capability to promote products through a different lens, with vivid sensorial activation for the future consumers of virtual products. IoT and Cloud can connect the organizations, suppliers and customers as platforms for offers, platforms being able to collect information regarding the consumer behavior which organizations can use to improve service design.

Exchange aims at substituting the inefficient products with sustainable ones. AM adoption and IoT can advance the manufacturing production to reduce waste generation, to ease waste collection, separation and recycling. Collaborative robotics are by themselves an upgrade in terms of equipment efficiency and can optimize the continuous flow of production (Despeisse, 2017).

As far as consumers are concerned, technologies can play an important role as well. AM can foster the purchase behavior for customers as they offer new and attractive solutions to the market. 3D printing is looked into by many and if accessible on the market, will stir customers to engage in purchase behavior. AR and Simulations can offer customers visualizations of how the end-of-life of products can look like and can offer companies the model of how end-of-life should look like. Moreover, this can bring advertising strategies to reach the desired outcomes from the consumers. BDA can play an extremely important role in the fostering the consumer behavior to benefit from the I4.0 technologies. Moreover, IoT and cloud technologies are helpful as information sharing networks, platforms for connectivity and

easier access to stored information, all protected through Cybersecurity. As a complementary approach, collaborative robots can mend where consumers cannot accomplish the desired separate collection rates, they can separately collect the waste.

Given the fact that humanity has gone through difficult times due to the Covid virus, we must all the more align ourselves with SD, which has as its main goal the good of society along with economic prosperity and a clean environment, in this context production and consumption behavior playing a key role.

CE will develop further as well, through the described technologies. There is still room for filling in the gap about what is the impact of industry 4.0 on the circular consumer behavior. CE promises an action-oriented approach to achieve SD, therefore, the use from technology and innovation cannot be missed (Lakatos, 2021; Székely, 2020). It is an imperative that CE entails smart technologies which can facilitate the transition.

The technologies development and the improvements in the manufacturing procedures have created room for efficiency and performance through robots, IoT, easy communication systems with online networks and virtual realities, representing means for predicting patterns and correlations for more data-based decisions making in the future.

Companies can combine CE and technologies for reasearch and influencing the circular behaviour patterns, to redesign circular business models for met a SD with associated benefits in terms of economics, society and environment, so necessary things in this COVID-19 pandemic context.

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